

1 **Supplementary table legend**

- 2 • **Table S1** Baseline clinical characteristics
- 3 • **Table S2** Demographic and clinical characteristics of WDEIA in Thailand and Hong
- 4 Kong
- 5 • **Table S3** Two by two contingency table showing true positive, false positive, true
- 6 negative, false negative comparing skin prick test to gliadin with the standard
- 7 diagnostic criteria of WDEIA

8 **Table S1 Baseline clinical characteristics**

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Characteristics	WDEIA (n=62)	Control (n=62)	<i>p</i> -value
Male	25 (40.32)	25 (40.32)	1.000
Current age, years (median (IQR))	44.5 (32-55)	42 (32-56)	0.985
Atopic comorbidities			
• Allergic rhinitis	28 (45.16)	24 (38.71)	0.585
• Asthma/COPD	4 (6.45)	6 (9.68)	0.743
• Other food allergy	13 (20.97)	15 (24.19)	0.830
• Any drug allergy	12 (19.35)	19 (30.65)	0.213
Other comorbidities			
• Diabetes mellitus	3 (4.84)	6 (9.68)	0.491
• Hypertension	7 (11.29)	8 (12.90)	1.000

10 Present in n (%) unless otherwise specified.

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12 **Abbreviations:** COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; IQR, interquartile range; SD,
13 standard deviation; WDEIA, wheat-dependent exercise-induced anaphylaxis

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Table S2 Demographic and clinical characteristics of WDEIA in Thailand and Hong Kong

Characteristics	All WDEIA cases (n=62)	Thai WDEIA cases (n=32)	Hong Kong WDEIA cases (n=30)	p-value
Demographic data				
Male	25 (40.32)	9 (28.12)	16 (53.33)	0.069
Age at first onset, years (median (IQR))	33 (22-45)	27 (17.5-38.5)	41.5 (26-50)	0.007
Age at diagnosis, years (median (IQR))	39 (28-51)	33 (22-39.5)	50 (34-62)	<0.001
Time from onset to diagnosis, years (median (IQR))	3 (1-6)	2 (0.5-4)	4.5 (1-10)	0.032
Number of episodes before diagnosis (median (IQR))	5 (3-10)	4 (2-5)	10 (5-18)	<0.001
Atopic comorbidities				
• Allergic rhinitis	28 (45.16)	19 (59.38)	9 (30.00)	0.024
• Asthma/COPD	4 (6.45)	3 (9.38)	1 (3.33)	0.613
• Other food allergy	13 (20.97)	8 (25.00)	5 (16.67)	0.537
• Any drug allergy	12 (19.35)	3 (9.38)	9 (30.00)	0.055
Clinical characteristics at most severe reaction				
• Mucocutaneous system	62 (100.00)	32 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	1.000
• Respiratory system	48 (77.42)	19 (59.38)	29 (96.67)	0.001
• Cardiovascular system	54 (87.10)	27 (84.38)	27 (99.00)	0.709
• Gastrointestinal system	18/61 (29.51)	14/31 (45.16)	4 (13.33)	0.011
Investigations				
• Specific IgE †				
○ sIgE wheat, kU/L (range, min-max)	0.47 (0.01-10.9)	0.56 (0.05-10.9)	0.37 (0.01-8.11)	0.317
○ sIgE wheat positive rate (%)	34/58 (60.71)	22/32 (68.75)	12/26 (46.15)	0.110
○ sIgE o5g, kU/L (range, min-max)	3.88 (0-50.1)	3.13 (0-50.1)	4.95 (0.1-46.1)	0.283
○ sIgE o5g positive rate (%)	54/60 (91.67)	29/32 (90.62)	26/28 (92.86)	1.000
• SPT positive ‡				
○ In-house gliadin extract	58/59 (98.31)	28/29 (96.55)	30/30 (100.00)	0.492
○ Commercial wheat extract	15/59 (25.42)	1/29 (3.45)	14/30 (46.67)	<0.001
○ Barley extract	7/57 (12.28)	4/31 (12.90)	3/26 (11.54)	1.000
○ Oat extract	6/56 (10.71)	2/30 (6.67)	4/26 (15.38)	0.401

○ Rye extract	8/61 (13.11)	3/31 (9.68)	5/30 (16.67)	0.473
○ Wheat (real food)	24/30 (80.00)	NA	24/30 (80.0)	NA

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18 Present in n (%) unless otherwise specified

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20 † ImmunoCAP. Positive test result is defined by a level of allergen-specific IgE \geq 0.35
21 kAU/L.

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23 ‡ Positive test result is defined by a wheal diameter larger than 3 mm compared with the
24 negative control. Histamine phosphate (10 mg/mL) and glycerinated saline were used as the
25 positive and negative controls.

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28 **Abbreviations:** COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; IQR, interquartile range;
29 MWD, mean wheal diameter; med, median; NA, not available; ns, non-specific antigen; o5g,
30 omega-5 gliadin; ST, skin test, using skin prick test method; SD, standard deviation; sIgE,
31 specific IgE; WDEIA, wheat-dependent exercise-induced anaphylaxis

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34 **Table S3** Two by two contingency table and diagnostic indices of SPT Gliadin and SPT
 35 wheat results comparing to standard diagnostic criteria of WDEIA.
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SPT results	All WDEIA cases	Controls	Total
SPT Gliadin (n=123)			
Positive (MWD \geq 3 mm)	60	0	60
Negative MWD <3 mm)	1	62	63
Total	61	62	123
Sensitivity (%) (95% CI)		98.4 (91.2-100.0)	
Specificity (%) (95% CI)		100.0 (94.2-100.0)	
AuROC		0.95 (0.90-0.99)	
SPT Wheat (n=89)			
Positive (\geq 3x3 mm)	15	0	15
Negative (<3x3 mm)	44	30	74
Total	59	30	89
Sensitivity (%) (95% CI)		25.4 (15.0-38.4)	
Specificity (%) (95% CI)		100.0 (88.4 – 100.0)	
AuROC		0.63 (0.57-0.68)	

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38 **Abbreviations:** AuROC, area under the curve of receiver operating characteristic curve; CI,
 39 confidence interval; mm, millimetre; SPT, skin prick test, using skin prick test method;
 40 WDEIA, wheat-dependent exercise-induced anaphylaxis
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45 **Supplementary figure legends**

46 • **Figure S1** Study flow diagram

47 • **Figure S2** Specific IgE test for wheat and omega-5-gliadin (O5G) in Thai and Hong

48 Kong WDEIA cases

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Figure S1 Study flow diagram

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57 **Figure S2** Specific IgE test for wheat (left) and omega-5-gliadin (right) in Thai and Hong
 58 Kong WDEIA cases. Data are presented as geometric mean and 95% confidence interval.
 59 Non-parametric test was used to compare MWD between Thai and Hongkong WDEIA cases.

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61 **Abbreviations:** ns, not significant; O5G, omega-5-gliadin; WDEIA, wheat-dependent
 62 exercise induced anaphylaxis

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